

Automated Energy Smell Refactoring of Java Code: an LLM Agents-based Approach

Guido Maria Di Fiore¹, Juri Di Rocco¹, and Henry Muccini¹

¹Department of Information Engineering, Computer Science and Mathematics (DISIM), University of L'Aquila, Italy
guidomaria.difiore@graduate.univaq.it {juri.dirocco, henry.muccini}@univaq.it

Abstract. *Green Software Engineering* is gaining traction. However, most existing information technology platforms rely on legacy systems whose manual energy optimization is costly and error-prone. A key challenge is the identification and resolution of *energy smells*—code patterns indicative of energy inefficiency—which require both detection expertise and safe refactoring that preserves functional behavior.

This paper presents an LLM-based Multi-Agent System (MAS) that automates energy-oriented refactoring of Java code. The system uses SonarQube, augmented with energy-specific plugins (Creedengo, aixigo), to detect energy smells via static analysis. Then, a team of LLM-based agents, orchestrated through the CrewAI framework, iteratively analyzes, refactors, and validates each class in a self-correcting loop.

The approach was validated on 24 open-source Java projects across two complexity levels: 12 student projects (1–3k LOC, 611 total issues) and 12 professional codebases from Apache Commons and Spring (up to 70k LOC, 6,119 total issues). Results show an average energy smell reduction of 65.36% on student projects, with a peak reduction of 97.22%. For enterprise projects, we observe an average reduction of 27.18% across all cases, increasing to 32.62% when excluding the two total-failure cases, namely commons-configuration and commons-math, with a peak reduction of 64.86%. These reductions are achieved while keeping test suite success rates close to 100%. However, the dynamic energy analysis conducted with JoularJX suggests that resolving static energy smells does not necessarily translate into runtime energy savings.

Keywords: Green Software Engineering · Energy Smells · Automated Refactoring · Multi-Agent Systems · Large Language Models (LLM) · Software Energy Efficiency

1 Introduction

The growing energy footprint of software-intensive systems raises important sustainability concerns. In response to this need and to EU Regulations [4], *Green Software Engineering* practices have been introduced to support the design and development of software that is not only functional and efficient, but also attentive to its energy footprint [21,3]. While new engineers are being trained to write

energy-aware code, a vast amount of existing software-intensive systems are built upon *legacy systems* where energy optimization was never a design goal. Manual refactoring of such codebases to improve energy efficiency is prohibitively expensive, time-consuming, and error-prone. The challenge lies not only in identifying the problematic code patterns—the so-called *energy smells*—but also in applying correct transformations that maintain functional equivalence while reducing energy waste [10]. A code smell is, in general, a pattern that indicates a deeper structural or design problem, potentially causing future bugs, maintenance difficulties, technical debt, or resource waste. An *energy smell* is thus a code smell indicative of possible energy inefficiency [12,18]. To identify energy smells, two main approaches exist: static analysis, that directly identifies code lines that violate predefined coding rules, and dynamic analysis, that physically measures the energy consumption of a running program [15].

This paper presents an approach that, by means of static analysis, automates energy-oriented refactoring of existing Java code. The approach leverages source code analysis performed by SonarQube, augmented with energy-specific plugins, to *identify* energy smells. Then, these issues are automatically *resolved* by a team of LLM-based agents orchestrated through the CrewAI framework, operating in an iterative, self-correcting cycle. The energy consumed by the original system and its restructured counterpart is measured, collected, and comparatively analyzed.

The proposed approach was validated on two distinct datasets: 12 student projects (small-scale, 1–3k LOC) and 12 professional/enterprise projects from the Apache Commons and Spring ecosystems (up to 70k LOC). The evaluation addresses two research questions covering: (RQ1) effectiveness and correctness of energy smell reduction, and (RQ2) static smell resolution correspondence to energy savings.

The main contributions of this paper are as follows:

- An LLM-based multi-agent system (MAS) architecture combining SonarQube static analysis with LLM-based refactoring agents for automated energy smell resolution.
- An empirical validation on 24 Java projects spanning different complexity levels, demonstrating the system’s effectiveness and limitations.
- A dynamic energy consumption analysis using JoularJX that reveals the gap between static smell resolution and actual runtime energy savings.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the background and key technologies. Section 3 describes the proposed approach in detail. Section 4 presents the evaluation methodology, datasets, and research questions. Section 5 discusses the results, while Section 6 discusses known limitations. Section 7 surveys related work, and Section 8 concludes the paper and outlines future work.

2 Background

This section provides the background required to understand the technological foundations of our approach. In particular, Section 2.1 introduces SonarQube, which we use to identify energy-related code issues through static analysis, while Section 2.2 describes CrewAI, the framework adopted to orchestrate the multi-agent workflow underlying the automated refactoring process.

2.1 SonarQube

SonarQube is an open-source platform developed by Sonar¹ that enables static code analysis and automatic extraction of quality attributes according to specific rules. Approximately 4,000 rules are available by default for 24 programming languages, and this set can be extended through third-party plugins. Focusing on energy-specific issues, we identified 3 different plugins related to energy efficiency, i.e., *Creedengo* [9], *SonarQube Java Energy Impact Plugin* [1], and *GreenForLoops* [7]. The Creedengo plugin targets optimizations of CPU cycles, memory allocation, and disk/network I/O operations. Code inefficiency brings higher and longer computing, which directly translates into higher electricity consumption [12,18]. Among the 100 rules defined in the Creedengo repository,² we have analyzed the 16 over 17 concretely implemented in the SonarQube plugins.³ The SonarQube Java Energy Impact Plugin provides a single rule for managing collections. GreenForLoops was excluded due to configuration issues that prevented correct system operation. In addition to these plugins, 35 additional rules were selected from SonarQube’s standard collection—specifically, all those tagged with *performance*—to remain consistent with the Performance-as-Efficiency paradigm also used by Creedengo’s rules. The rules introduced by the two retained plugins are summarized in Appendix Table 3.

2.2 CrewAI

CrewAI is an open-source framework designed to orchestrate autonomous AI agents and support the development of complex workflows⁴. Its architecture is based on two core concepts: *Flows*, which model event-driven workflows, and *Crews*, which denote teams of agents collaborating within a *Flow* toward a common goal.

A *Flow* coordinates the execution logic of the system by combining *i*) *Agents* grouped into *Crews* and *ii*) deterministic Python tools executed locally. During execution, it maintains a shared *state*, which allows intermediate information to be stored and passed across the workflow.

¹ <https://www.sonarsource.com/>

² <https://github.com/green-code-initiative/creedengo-rules-specifications/blob/main/RULES.md>

³ we discarded rule GC182 since it consistently produced false positives in all test projects

⁴ <https://docs.crewai.com/en/introduction>

An *Agent* is an autonomous unit designed to perform a specific function within a *Crew*. It is characterized by three main attributes: *Role*, which defines its responsibility; *Goal*, which specifies the objective guiding its decisions according to a goal-based agent design [20]; and *Backstory*, which provides contextual information to enrich the prompt given to the LLM. Additional configuration options include the LLM to be used, custom tools, the maximum number of iterations, and verbosity settings.

Finally, a *Task* is the assignment given to an *Agent*. *Tasks* can be collaborative, requiring the cooperation of multiple agents. Once *Agents* and their *Tasks* are declared, a *Crew* of collaborative agents can be assembled and executed.

3 Proposed Approach

This section describes the design and implementation of the multi-agent system for automated energy smell refactoring. The complete source code is available at: <https://anonymous.4open.science/r/GitHub-Prototipo-CrewAI-Sequel-8F15>.

3.1 System Architecture Overview

Figure 1 illustrates the architecture of the proposed multi-agent system for automated energy smell refactoring. The system is composed of three main layers: input artifacts, pre-analysis, and crew-based execution. The approach takes as input a *Java Project*, which represents the target system to be analyzed and refactored.

Pre-analysis Module. This module relies on *SonarQube* to perform an initial static analysis of the project. It extracts three key elements: (i) the list of *issues*, with a focus on energy-related smells, (ii) the *source code* of the identified hotspots, and (iii) the corresponding *file paths*. These artifacts constitute the input for the refactoring process.

Crew Execution Environment. The core of the system is a pipeline of coordinated agents organized as a *Crew*. The Crew includes:

- **Query Writer (LLM-based).** This agent is responsible for *generating a structured refactoring strategy* in the form of a prompt. It analyzes the input code, the detected issues, and any available feedback from previous iterations (e.g., compilation errors or newly introduced issues). Based on this information, it dynamically adapts the prompt to guide subsequent refactoring attempts more effectively.
- **Code Refactor (LLM-based).** This agent executes the refactoring strategy produced by the Query Writer. It applies the suggested transformations and *returns a complete, refactored version of the source code*, ensuring that no placeholders or partial outputs are generated.
- **Code Replacer (deterministic).** This component is responsible for concretely applying the refactoring by *replacing the original source file* with the refactored version generated by the Code Refactor agent. It ensures consistency between the generated output and the project structure.

- **Sonar Agent (deterministic)**. This agent performs validation by triggering a new SonarQube analysis. It verifies both the compilation correctness of the refactored code and the effectiveness of the refactoring in reducing the number of detected issues.
- **Errors Summarizer (LLM-based)**. Activated when validation fails, this agent analyzes compilation errors or verification issues and produces a concise diagnostic summary. This feedback is then provided to the Query Writer to inform and improve the next iteration.

Fig. 1: High-level overview of the proposed approach.

The architecture also includes a decision node that evaluates whether the refactoring attempt was successful (i.e., no build failures and no new issues introduced). Based on this evaluation, the system either terminates successfully or triggers a new iteration. Finally, the output of the process is a refactored version of the original system that is expected to exhibit improved energy efficiency.

3.2 Execution Flow

The system operates through an autonomous and iterative workflow composed of two main phases, i.e., Hotspot Identification and Iterative Refactoring Loop.

Phase 1 – Hotspot Identification. The pre-analysis module extracts the top N most critical classes based on the number of detected issues.

Phase 2 – Iterative Refactoring Loop. For each selected class, the Crew executes an iterative refinement cycle where the *Query Writer* agent generates a refactoring prompt from the source code, the detected issues, and, when available, feedback from previous failed attempts. The *Code Refactor* agent uses this prompt to produce the refactored version of the class. The *Code Replacer* component applies the generated changes to the original source file. The *Sonar Agent* then validates the result by checking whether the project still compiles and whether the number of issues has decreased. If the validation fails, the *Errors Summarizer* agent extracts the relevant failure information, such as compilation errors or newly introduced issues, and feeds it back to the next iteration.

The loop ends either when the maximum number of attempts is reached or when all issues are successfully resolved.

A key design principle of the system is robustness: at each iteration, the last successfully compiled version is preserved. If all attempts fail, the system retains the best available version—defined as the one that compiles and exhibits fewer issues than the original—ensuring that even partial improvements are not lost.

4 Evaluation Methodology

This section describes the empirical design adopted to evaluate the proposed approach. We first present the methodology and metrics used to assess the refactoring process (Section 4.2). We then describe the dataset, which includes both student projects and professional Java codebases, allowing us to observe the behavior of the approach under different levels of size, complexity, and test availability (Section 4.3). Finally, we formulate the research questions guiding the evaluation, focusing on two complementary aspects: the effectiveness and correctness of energy-smell reduction, and the extent to which static improvements correspond to actual runtime energy savings (Section 4.1).

4.1 Research Questions

The following research questions guide the evaluation:

RQ1: Effectiveness and Correctness of Energy Smell Reduction. To what extent can an automated multi-agent approach reduce energy smells in Java source code, and does the refactoring compromise the original functional correctness of the software?

RQ2: Static vs. Dynamic Analysis Gap. To what extent does the reduction of statically-detected energy smells impact the actual energy consumption of the program at runtime?

4.2 Methodology and Metrics

The validation follows the same workflow implemented by the proposed approach: initial analysis, hotspot selection, iterative refactoring, and final project-level validation. Each project belonging to the curated dataset (Section 4.3) is first analyzed with SonarQube to obtain the baseline values used for comparison. The collected metrics include the number of energy-related issues, lines of code, code duplications, and, when available, test coverage and test success rate. Since student projects do not include automated test suites, testing-related metrics are considered only for professional projects. For each project, classes are ranked according to the number of detected energy-related issues. The refactoring process is applied to the 10 classes with the most energy-related issues identified. This threshold limits the analysis to the most relevant hotspots while keeping the execution cost manageable. Two exclusion criteria are applied before refactoring.

First, classes longer than 3,500 lines of code are discarded, since large inputs increase the risk of incomplete or unreliable LLM outputs. The iterative refactoring loop is limited to four attempts per class to bound the number of LLM calls and validation runs. After all selected classes have been processed, a final SonarQube analysis is executed on the complete project.

For professional projects that include test cases, we execute them by JaCoCo⁵. It allows us to observe changes in coverage and test success rate after refactoring. In particular, for RQ2, the static analysis is complemented with dynamic energy measurements on the professional projects for which execution was possible. The evaluation relies on the following metrics:

- Lines of code (LOC);
- Energy-related issues: number of SonarQube issues associated with energy smells before and after refactoring.
- Smell reduction for each project is computed from the Issues column of Table 1 as $(\text{Issues}_A - \text{Issues}_{A'}) / \text{Issues}_A$ in %. Reported averages are the arithmetic mean of these per-project reduction rates.
- Failed refactorings: number of selected classes for which the system did not produce an accepted refactoring.
- Execution time: total time required to complete the refactoring process for a project.
- Test success rate: percentage of passing tests after refactoring, computed for professional projects only.
- Test Code coverage: coverage measured through JaCoCo for professional projects.
- Energy consumption is measured with JoularJX⁶ by running each project test suite five times before and five times after refactoring, in order to reduce the impact of measurement noise and compare the resulting average values.

4.3 Dataset

The approach was validated on two categories of open-source Java projects from GitHub. The first category consists of 12 student projects from the LPODISIM2023 organization⁷, developed for an Object-Oriented Programming Lab course. The students who developed the projects are first-year undergraduate students. The second category consists of 12 professional/enterprise projects, including various Apache Commons libraries⁸ and Spring PetClinic⁹. Table 1 summarizes the selected projects and their initial metrics. The student projects were developed as group assignments and did not include automated test suites, unlike the professional projects. Overall, the initial dataset comprises a total of 6,730 energy smell issues, of which 6,119 belong to the professional projects and 611 to the student

⁵ <https://github.com/jacoco/jacoco>

⁶ <https://github.com/joular/joularjx>

⁷ <https://github.com/LPODISIM2023>

⁸ <https://www.apache.org/projects/>

⁹ <https://spring-petclinic.github.io/>

Table 1: Initial and post-refactoring metrics for all projects.

ID	Project	LOC	Issues		Coverage		Test Success		Failures	Time (s)
			A → A'	Reduction	Initial	After	Initial	After		
S1	Project 1	2k	53 → 10	81.13 %	-	-	-	-	1	1672
S2	Project 2	2.1k	54 → 43	20.37 %	-	-	-	-	7	2095
S3	Project 3	2.3k	62 → 28	54.84 %	-	-	-	-	1	1377
S4	Project 4	1.8k	109 → 23	78.90 %	-	-	-	-	1	1582
S5	Project 5	2.7k	32 → 9	71.88 %	-	-	-	-	2	1492
S6	Project 6	1.7k	50 → 3	4.00 %	-	-	-	-	0	778
S7	Project 7	1.9k	62 → 16	74.19 %	-	-	-	-	1	1313
S8	Project 8	1.4k	36 → 1	97.22 %	-	-	-	-	0	1436
S9	Project 9	1.5k	28 → 26	7.14 %	-	-	-	-	3	1519
S10	Project 10	1.8k	50 → 7	86.00 %	-	-	-	-	2	1644
S11	Project 11	1.7k	36 → 9	75.00 %	-	-	-	-	1	1904
S12	Project 12	1.1k	39 → 22	43.59 %	-	-	-	-	5	1683
P1	spring-petclinic	1.3k	5 → 3	40.00 %	91.9%	91.9%	100%	100%	0	327
P2	commons-compress	45k	1344 → 971	27.75 %	84.6%	84.2%	100%	99.1%	3	4951
P3	commons-lang	33k	856 → 765	10.63 %	95.3%	94.9%	2%	2%	6	8423
P4	commons-beanutils	9.1k	252 → 179	28.97 %	74.8%	75.1%	99.8%	99.4%	2	3302
P5	commons-codec	11k	346 → 176	49.13 %	94.7%	94.7%	100%	99.8%	4	5839
P6	commons-configuration	21k	548 → 548	0.00 %	91.1%	91.1%	100%	100%	10	6018
P7	commons-dbc	14k	125 → 97	22.40 %	68.2%	68.0%	100%	100%	1	2969
P8	commons-dbtutils	3.6k	37 → 13	64.86 %	70.8%	71.0%	100%	99.8%	1	2177
P9	commons-math	70k	1878 → 1878	0.00 %	74.6%	74.6%	100%	100%	10	10058
P10	commons-net	18k	203 → 137	32.51 %	37.3%	37.4%	100%	100%	1	3432
P11	commons-pool	6.5k	113 → 84	25.66 %	87.8%	87.9%	100%	100%	2	3497
P12	commons-text	11k	412 → 312	24.27 %	98.8%	98.8%	100%	99.9%	4	5198

*Coverage and Test Success averages are computed only on professional projects.

projects. The two datasets differ in two key aspects: student project identifiers were anonymized for privacy; student projects lack unit tests (as testing was not required in the course), whereas enterprise projects include automated test suites used to assess the quality and safety of the refactoring, and to measure their runtime energy consumption.

5 Results

This section reports the results of our empirical evaluation, structured around two research questions. First, we assess the effectiveness of the proposed approach in reducing statically detected energy smells and its ability to preserve the functional correctness of the refactored projects in Section 5.1. Second, Section 5.2 investigates whether the reduction of static energy smells translates into actual energy savings at runtime by comparing pre- and post-refactoring energy measurements collected with JoularJX.

5.1 RQ1: Effectiveness and Correctness of Energy Smell Reduction

RQ1 investigates whether the proposed approach can reduce energy smells while preserving the functional correctness of the refactored software. To this end, we

structure the analysis along three dimensions. First, we measure the *reduction of statically detected energy smells* to assess the effectiveness of the refactoring process. Second, we examine *correctness by considering test success rate and coverage* for professional projects, and manual executions for student projects where automated tests are not available. Third, we analyze the *impact of context complexity*, since project size, architectural structure, and code interdependencies may affect both the success rate and the execution time of the multi-agent system. Together, these dimensions provide a more complete view of the practical viability of the approach beyond the mere reduction of SonarQube issues.

Smell Reduction. The analysis of the data in Table 1 demonstrates that the approach is effective at reducing energy smells, albeit with varying efficacy depending on the application context. For student projects, the system achieved excellent results, with an average smell reduction of 65.36%, reaching peaks of 97.22% (Student 8). For enterprise codebases, excluding cases of total failure where the code remained unaltered, the average reduction was 27.18% across all cases, increasing to 32.62% when excluding the two total-failure cases, namely `commons-configuration` and `commons-math`. Noteworthy reductions include 64.86% for `commons-dbutils` (3.6k LOC), 49.26% for `commons-codec` (11k LOC), and 27.75% for `commons-compress` (45k LOC). The system thus proves to be a valid and functional approach for automatic energy smell reduction. Its measurable effectiveness is very high on less complex code, while maintaining a more limited but still significant impact on enterprise codebases.

Functional Correctness. For student projects, since unit test implementation was not required during the original development, concrete measurement through automated test suites was not possible. Manual executions and validations were performed, revealing no evident bugs, crashes, or anomalous exceptions. For enterprise codebases, the presence of native unit tests provided solid quantitative data. As shown in Table 1, in many cases the test success rate remained unchanged. In the limited cases where a decrease was observed, it remained below 1% with respect to the original version (e.g., `commons-compress` with -0.9% , `commons-dbutils` with -0.2%). This behavior can be explained by the scope of the refactoring process. The approach targets only production classes identified as hotspots, while test classes are left unchanged. As a consequence, the refactoring is constrained to preserve existing interfaces and observable behavior, since any incompatibility would immediately surface as test failures. Minor variations in test success rate are therefore attributable to indirect effects of the refactoring (e.g., subtle behavioral changes, stricter validations, or timing-related differences), rather than structural inconsistencies. The anomalous 2% test success rate of `commons-lang` is present already in the unmodified baseline and is attributable to a test-environment configuration issue independent of our refactoring; notably, the rate remained unchanged after refactoring, consistent with the preservation of observable behavior. Overall, the limited impact on test outcomes suggests that the approach mainly preserves functional correctness,

even without adapting the associated test suites. The overall test coverage also experienced minimal variations of fractions of a percentage point. In summary, the approach effectively reduces energy smells—with high efficacy on simpler codebases and moderate but significant impact on enterprise systems—while preserving almost entirely the functional correctness of the original software.

Context complexity. The analysis clearly demonstrates that student projects are significantly “easier” to optimize for the multi-agent system, both in terms of effectiveness and execution time. Student projects achieved an average energy smell reduction of 65.36%, with peaks of 97.22%. Enterprise codebases, characterized by greater structural complexity, deep interdependencies, and rigid architectural patterns, registered a lower average reduction of 32.62%. Additionally, enterprise projects show a significantly higher number of failed refactoring attempts; in complex cases such as `commons-configuration` and `commons-math`, 10 failures occurred leading to total approach failure. Regarding execution times, student projects completed in an average of approximately 25.6 minutes per project, while enterprise codebases required an average of approximately 78 minutes. In the worst case (`commons-math`, 70k LOC), the system spent nearly 3 hours attempting to resolve issues before failing definitively. The approach works excellently on projects of moderate size with linear logic typical of novice code. Facing enterprise and highly structured legacy code, temporal performance degrades notably and effectiveness decreases, highlighting the current limitations of LLM input/output/context window and complex architectural reasoning.

5.2 RQ2: Static vs. Dynamic Analysis Gap

To verify whether the reduction in statically detected issues corresponds to actual energy savings, dynamic analysis was conducted using JoularJX. Measurements were performed on 8 of the 12 enterprise projects, excluding the two total failures and two projects where measurement was not possible due to test-configuration issues. Energy consumption was measured during the execution of the identified test plans, relying on the JaCoCo-based test execution setup used to assess coverage and test success. For each project, five pre-refactoring and five post-refactoring measurements were collected, and the average value was computed.

The results (Table 2) reveal a heterogeneous scenario. The most promising result was recorded for `commons-pool`, which showed a 19.06% decrease in energy consumption alongside a 25.66% reduction in energy smells. However, in some projects the refactoring paradoxically generated increased energy consumption, with peaks of +21.73% for `commons-codec`. This well-known phenomenon in the literature [17] highlights how **the formal resolution of a code smell does not automatically guarantee hardware-level optimization**—adopting formally “cleaner” data structures or patterns can introduce computational overhead that negates the expected energy benefits.

To better understand to what extent the measured energy values could be affected by machine-dependent variability, we complemented the analysis of

Table 2: Comparison of estimated energy consumption (Joules) via JoularJX before and after refactoring.

Project	Pre-Refact. Mean (J)	Post-Refact. Mean (J)	Variation
spring-petclinic	581.292	557.462	-4.19%
commons-compress	4686.044	4882.522	+4.11%
commons-codec	706.110	878.242	+21.73%
commons-dbcp	1392.424	1499.496	+7.40%
commons-dbutils	221.736	237.790	+6.99%
commons-net	1151.556	1170.436	+1.63%
commons-pool	6368.850	5260.430	-19.06%
commons-text	2212.256	2219.848	+0.34%

mean energy consumption with a statistical validation using the non-parametric Mann–Whitney U test. Given the limited number of executions per configuration ($N = 5$ before and $N = 5$ after refactoring), this test allowed us to assess whether the observed differences were consistent enough to be distinguished from normal execution variability. Although Table 2 reports noticeable variations in the mean values, the statistical analysis showed that only `commons-codec` exhibited a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.01$), with a consistent increase in energy consumption after refactoring. Consequently, the absence of statistically significant differences in most projects indicates that the measured variations cannot yet be robustly attributed to the refactoring process. Future work should therefore extend this validation through a larger number of executions, more controlled experimental conditions, and additional workloads, enabling a stronger assessment of the relationship between static smell reduction and actual energy savings. These findings suggest that static analysis via SonarQube and dynamic consumption analysis do not seem to be aligned. The elimination of statically-detected energy smells does not guarantee substantial energy reductions at runtime, and in some confirmed scenarios it can even add persistent computational overhead. For reliable “green” refactoring, a careful review of static analysis rules is needed, potentially supplemented by direct integration of runtime energy measurement into the refactoring feedback loop.

6 Discussion and limitations

The proposed multi-agent system is not a *silver bullet* for energy-aware refactoring. While our results demonstrate its ability to reduce statically detected energy smells and preserve functional correctness in most cases, they also reveal important limitations affecting its robustness, scalability, and practical applicability. These limitations arise from the dependence on the selected LLM (Section 6.1), the difficulty of processing large and complex codebases within effective context and time constraints (Section 6.2), and the imperfect alignment between static energy-smell rules and actual runtime energy consumption (Section 6.3).

6.1 AI Model Selection

The system’s decision-making capability depends on the underlying LLM. Early versions employed `gemini-2.0-flash`, chosen for its quality/cost ratio. However, this model proved inefficient for complex classes, often leading to crashes, hallucinations, or infinite token repetition. After also testing `gemini-2.5-flash-lite`, which presented similar problems, the system adopted `gemini-2.5-flash`. Despite this, the AI demonstrated intrinsic difficulties in autonomously resolving certain specific refactoring rules. To overcome this cognitive limitation, it was necessary to inject specific resolution directives into the initial prompt for rules such as `AvoidJavaCollectionFramework` and `GC167`, in addition to removing rule `GC182` due to continuous false positives.

6.2 Scalability Limitations in Large and Complex Codebases

Although modern models declare extremely large context windows (up to one million tokens), the precision and effectiveness of the model degrade drastically with increasing input length and complexity. This structural limitation necessitated inserting a selection threshold in the approach, excluding all files longer than 3,500 lines from refactoring. Scalability is further challenged by the temporal cost of the retry-and-validate cycle. When the LLM encounters code with high complexity, the retry-and-validate cycle lengthens critically, incurring enormous time costs. The most extreme case occurred with `commons-math` (70k LOC), where the system spent nearly 3 hours before failing definitively. This also prevents adopting a more “modular” approach of addressing one issue at a time per file, which could yield more effective refactoring but at unsustainable execution times.

6.3 Static and Dynamic Energy Assessment

A further limitation concerns the gap between static energy-smell detection and actual runtime energy consumption. Although our approach is guided by SonarQube rules specifically selected to capture performance- and energy-related inefficiencies, the dynamic analysis conducted with JoularJX shows that removing statically detected issues does not necessarily translate into measurable energy savings. In our experiments, the measurements were based on a limited number of executions, and most observed variations were not statistically significant according to the Mann–Whitney U test. This means that, for most projects, the measured differences between pre- and post-refactoring energy consumption cannot be confidently attributed to the refactoring itself, as they may fall within normal execution noise. This limitation highlights two important aspects. First, it confirms that static analysis is not always able to accurately predict the actual energy consumption of a program at runtime [11]. While energy-smell rules can identify code patterns that are potentially inefficient, their removal does not necessarily lead to measurable energy savings, since runtime consumption depends on input data, execution paths, JVM behavior, hardware characteristics, and

the overhead introduced by alternative implementations. Second, the mismatch between static and dynamic results suggests that the energy-related plugins and rules adopted in this study may require further refinement and validation. Our approach effectively reduces the number of statically detected energy issues, but the JoularJX results indicate that some of these rules may not be sufficiently aligned with actual runtime energy behavior. Thus, the observed gap should not be interpreted only as a limitation of the refactoring process, but also as evidence that current static rules may not always provide reliable proxies for energy consumption.

7 Related Work

This section discusses the main research streams related to our work. First, Section 7.1 reviews studies investigating the role of energy-consumption awareness in software engineering, with particular attention to developers’ ability to recognize, measure, and address energy-related inefficiencies during development. Then, Section 7.2 reports approaches that use refactoring techniques and, more recently, LLM-based agents to improve software energy efficiency. Finally, we position our contribution with respect to these works, highlighting how our approach combines static energy-smell detection, multi-agent automated refactoring, and dynamic energy-consumption assessment.

7.1 Energy Consumption Awareness in Software Engineering

The attention to energy consumption during software development is a relatively recent concern. In a study by Pang et al. [14], a survey of 122 professional programmers revealed that the vast majority lack the knowledge, tools, and awareness necessary to write sustainable code. Only 18% of respondents consider energy consumption during development, and barely 14% regard it as a genuine project requirement. Furthermore, only 10% had ever measured the energy impact of their software, using inadequate methods that do not permit fine-grained per-instruction tracing. Critically, only a small percentage of developers, when presented with 7 notoriously energy-inefficient bad practices, actually recognized them as critical energy problems. Jagroep et al. [8] further highlighted how developers and stakeholders at a major company lacked real awareness of the energy impact of their software products. The study revealed that the main cause of developer frustration was the concrete inability to identify energy anti-patterns within the software, underscoring the importance of a “knowledge bank” containing tactics, design patterns, and best practices specific to green software. Moises et al. [12] conducted a systematic literature review that extracted 170 practices across 7 main categories from 23 validated studies, clearly distinguishing between *Green BY Software* (software as a tool for sustainability in other sectors) and *Green IN Software* (sustainable software engineering itself). The most numerous category, Practices of Energy Consumption (PEC), highlighted 70 specific practices related to power optimization, CPU usage, memory, and application performance.

7.2 Code Refactoring and LLMs for Energy Efficiency

Pinto et al. [16] highlighted how refactoring has historically focused on extensibility, reusability, testability, and performance, while neglecting energy efficiency. Their study identified 14 high-quality empirical studies and 11 refactoring opportunities across macro-areas including mobile platforms, concurrent and parallel programming, approximate computing, and CPU management.

Regarding automated AI-driven refactoring guided by energy consumption, several recent approaches are noteworthy. Dearing et al. [2] proposed LASSI-EE, an iterative, self-corrective LLM-based framework that compiles code, executes it, and measures energy consumption in real time. Instead of relying on static analysis, the AI receives actual consumption profiles and creates contextual refactoring plans. A novel “LLM-as-a-Judge” agent validates functional equivalence, introducing the *energy-reduction@k* metric. With $k = 3$, the approach achieves nearly 50% energy savings with a 97% success rate, though it is limited to scientific parallel codes on GPUs. Scheffler et al. [19] presented EnerAgent, designed as a finite state machine via LangGraph, where the LLM first generates a functionally correct solution and then enters a dedicated energy optimization phase using CodeCarbon for consumption tracking. Through chain-of-thought prompting, the agent analyzes code step-by-step and replaces inefficiencies. The approach achieved an average 20% consumption reduction in over half of tested tasks, though it operates on LLM-generated code rather than legacy codebases. Oueslati et al. [13] presented RefAgent, a multi-agent framework closer to our approach. RefAgent focuses on structural code smells and QMOOD [6] quality metrics on Java projects, using specialized agents for planning, refactoring, compilation validation (up to 20 iterations), and testing (with EvoSuite [5] for test generation). It achieved a median 52.5% reduction in code smells with a 90% test success rate and 87% compilation rate, with an F1-score of 80% for identifying refactoring areas compared to human developers.

Our approach differs from these works by specifically targeting energy smells through SonarQube-based static analysis with energy-specific plugins, and by validating the gap between static smell resolution and dynamic energy savings—a novel, not previously leveraged methodology in the literature.

8 Conclusions and Future Work

This paper presented the design, development, and validation of a Multi-Agent System (MAS) based on Large Language Models for the automated refactoring of Java source code oriented toward energy efficiency. The proposed approach combines SonarQube static analysis, augmented with energy-specific plugins, and the CrewAI framework for agent orchestration. The empirical validation on 24 Java projects demonstrated that the approach can effectively reduce energy smells while preserving functional correctness. On student projects, the system achieved an average reduction of 65.36% (peak 97.22%) in approximately 25.6 minutes per project. On enterprise codebases, the average reduction was 27.18% across all cases, increasing to 32.62% when excluding the two total-failure cases, namely

commons-configuration and commons-math, with execution times averaging 78 minutes and peaking near 3 hours for the most complex projects. Test suite success rates remained very close to 100% across all enterprise projects that were successfully refactored. However, the dynamic energy analysis via JoularJX revealed a critical and counterintuitive finding: the reduction of statically-detected energy smells does not consistently translate into actual energy savings at runtime. While apparent consumption decreases proved statistically non-significant, in other projects a statistically confirmed increase in energy consumption was observed (up to +21.73%). This confirms that replacing certain data structures and patterns, while producing formally “cleaner” code according to static analysis rules, can introduce computational overhead that negates the expected energy benefits.

The limitations discussed in Section 6 pose several promising directions emerge for future work. First, experimenting with different MAS architectures and agent configurations, as discussed in the design space outlined in Section 6.1, could further improve refactoring effectiveness by exploring alternative coordination strategies among agents. Second, integrating dynamic energy analysis directly into the agent feedback loop—drawing inspiration from frameworks such as LASSI-EE and EnerAgent—would enable the system to accept refactoring proposals only when the energy delta is demonstrably negative, addressing one of the key limitations identified in our static analysis pipeline (Section 6.3). Third, the same pipeline would benefit from the development of custom SonarQube rules tailored to energy-specific anti-patterns not yet covered by existing plugins, as well as from a machine learning mechanism capable of automatically discarding rules that statistically introduce runtime energy overhead. Finally, adopting Model Context Protocol (MCP) servers, e.g., Github MCP Server¹⁰, as envisioned in the scalability discussion of Section 6.2, could offer more flexible, albeit non-deterministic, integration with external analysis tools.

Acknowledgment

This paper was partially supported by the MOSAICO project (Management, Orchestration and Supervision of AI-agent COmmunities for reliable AI in software engineering) that has received funding from the European Union under the Horizon Research and Innovation Action (Grant Agreement No. 101189664) and Erasmus+ Alliance for Innovation project AIM-PRO – AI Literacy for Multidisciplinary Professional Readiness and Outreach (Grant Agreement No. 101245864) and by Movetia, the Swiss agency promoting exchange, mobility and cooperation in education, continuing education and youth work.

References

1. aixigo: sonarqube-java-energyimpact-plugin, <https://github.com/aixigo/sonarqube-java-energyimpact-plugin>

¹⁰ <https://github.com/github/github-mcp-server>

2. Dearing, M.T., Tao, Y., Wu, X., Lan, Z., Taylor, V.: Leveraging llms to automate energy-aware refactoring of parallel scientific codes (2026), <https://arxiv.org/abs/2505.02184>
3. Erasmus Mundus MSc. Programme: Software engineers for green deal (2026), <https://se4gd.lutsoftware.com/>
4. European Union: Directive (eu) 2022/2464 of the european parliament and of the council of 14 december 2022 amending regulation (eu) no 537/2014, directive 2004/109/ec, directive 2006/43/ec and directive 2013/34/eu, as regards corporate sustainability reporting (2022), <https://europa.eu>, oJ L 322, 16.12.2022, p. 15–80
5. Fraser, G., Arcuri, A.: Evosuite: automatic test suite generation for object-oriented software. In: Proceedings of the 19th ACM SIGSOFT Symposium and the 13th European Conference on Foundations of Software Engineering. pp. 416–419. ES-EC/FSE '11 (2011). <https://doi.org/10.1145/2025113.2025179>
6. Goyal, P.K., Joshi, G.: Qmood metric sets to assess quality of java program. In: 2014 International Conference on Issues and Challenges in Intelligent Computing Techniques (ICICT). pp. 520–533 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICICT.2014.6781337>
7. Gurung, R.P., Porras, J., Koistinaho, J.: Static code analysis for reducing energy code smells in different loop types: A case study in java (2024), <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10805324/>
8. Jagroep, E., Broekman, J., van der Werf, J.M.E., Lago, P., Brinkkemper, S., Blom, L., van Vliet, R.: Awakening awareness on energy consumption in software engineering. In: 2017 IEEE/ACM 39th International Conference on Software Engineering: Software Engineering in Society Track (ICSE-SEIS). pp. 76–85 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSE-SEIS.2017.10>
9. Le Goaer, O., Hertout, J.: ecocode: a sonarqube plugin for energy code smells (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3551349.3559518>
10. Malavolta, I., Stoico, V., Lago, P.: Ten years of teaching empirical software engineering in the context of energy-efficient software. In: Handbook on Teaching Empirical Software Engineering, pp. 209–253. Springer (2024)
11. Marantos, C., Salapas, K., Papadopoulos, L., Soudris, D.: A flexible tool for estimating applications performance and energy consumption through static analysis. *SN Computer Science* **2**(1), 21 (2021)
12. Moises, A.C., Malucelli, A., Reinehr, S.: Practices of energy consumption for sustainable software engineering. In: 2018 Ninth International Green and Sustainable Computing Conference (IGSC). pp. 1–6 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1109/IGCC.2018.8752151>
13. Oueslati, K., Lamothe, M., Khomh, F.: Refagent: A multi-agent llm-based framework for automatic software refactoring (2025)
14. Pang, C., Hindle, A., Adams, B., Hassan, A.E.: What do programmers know about software energy consumption? *IEEE Software* **33**(3), 83–89 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1109/MS.2015.83>
15. Pigazzini, I., Di Nucci, D., Fontana, F.A., Belotti, M.: Exploiting dynamic analysis for architectural smell detection: a preliminary study. In: 2022 48th Euromicro Conference on Software Engineering and Advanced Applications (SEAA). pp. 282–289 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1109/SEAA56994.2022.00051>
16. Pinto, G., Soares-Neto, F., Castor, F.: Refactoring for energy efficiency: A reflection on the state of the art. In: 2015 IEEE/ACM 4th International Workshop on Green and Sustainable Software. pp. 29–35 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1109/GREENS.2015.12>

17. Poy, O., Moraga, M.Á., García, F., Calero, C.: Impact on energy consumption of design patterns, code smells and refactoring techniques: A systematic mapping study. *Journal of Systems and Software* **222**, 112303 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jss.2024.112303>
18. Salesforce News: Green code: How software can help save the planet, <https://www.salesforce.com/news/stories/green-code-software/>
19. Scheffler, J., Westing, M.: Energagent: Energy-aware code refinement with llm-based agents. In: *EnviroInfo 2025*, pp. 111–120. Gesellschaft für Informatik e.V. (2025). https://doi.org/10.18420/env2025_9
20. Shen, Z., Gay, R.K.L., Tao, X.: Goal-based intelligent agents (2003)
21. Shenoy, S.S., Eeratta, R.: Green software development model: An approach towards sustainable software development. In: *2011 Annual IEEE India Conference*. pp. 1–6 (2011). <https://doi.org/10.1109/INDCON.2011.6139638>

A Appendix

Table 3: Energy optimization rules introduced by the Creedengo and aixigo plugins, grouped by category.

Category	Plugin	Rule	Rationale
LOOP & ITERATION	Creedengo	Avoid collection size in loop cond.	Prevents redundant <code>.size()</code> calls at every iteration
	Creedengo	No function calls in for-loop decl.	Moves invariant computation outside the hot path
	Creedengo	Avoid repository calls in loops	Eliminates N+1 query pattern on Spring Data repos
	Creedengo	Avoid SQL requests in loops	Batches DB access to reduce connection overhead
	Creedengo	Prefer <code>++i</code> over <code>i++</code>	Avoids temporary copy of the iterator value
DATA & MEMORY	Creedengo	Avoid static collections	Prevents memory leaks from JVM-lifetime objects
	Creedengo	Init builder/buffer with expected size	Reduces dynamic resizing and array-copy overhead
	Creedengo	Use <code>System.arraycopy</code>	Delegates to native memcp, faster than loops
	Creedengo	Mark variables as <code>final</code>	Enables JIT constant folding, signals immutability
DATABASE & I/O	aixigo	Avoid Java Collection Framework	Replaces boxed wrappers with primitive arrays
	Creedengo	Avoid <code>SELECT *</code> queries	Fetches only needed columns, less network cost
	Creedengo	<code>PreparedStatement</code> over <code>Statement</code>	Enables query plan caching, prevents injection
	Creedengo	No const params in batch updates	Avoids redundant bind-variable assignments
	Creedengo	Optimize read-file exceptions	Uses try-with-resources to guarantee closure
CONTROL FLOW	Creedengo	Free resources explicitly	Closes connections eagerly instead of via GC
	Creedengo	Avoid multiple if-else chains	Prefer switch/polymorphism, less branch complexity
	Creedengo	<code>Pattern.compile</code> only in static ctx	Compiles regex once, avoids repeated parsing
Creedengo	<code>orElseGet</code> over <code>orElse</code>	Defers default-value computation via lazy supplier	